

TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY AS A CORRELATE OF STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AWKA EDUCATION ZONE, ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract: The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 5,550 students (2,444 males and 3,106 females) across 267 schools, from which a sample of 400 students (200 males and 200 females) was selected through a multistage sampling procedure. Data were collected using a researcher-designed Teachers' Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (TSEQ) and students' English Language scores obtained from official records. The TSEQ, consisting of 20 items on a four-point Likert scale, was validated by academic experts and demonstrated high reliability (Cronbach's alpha = 0.87) from a pilot study. Out of 160 questionnaires administered, 148 were returned and analyzed. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to determine the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic performance at a 0.05 significance level. The finding of the study revealed a high positive relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. Furthermore, findings of this study revealed a high positive relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the academic achievement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended among others that the Post Primary Schools Services Commission (PPSSC) and school administrators in public secondary schools should prioritise the professional development of teachers to strengthen their instructional self-efficacy. It was also recommended that teachers should be encouraged to adopt teaching approaches that accommodate diverse learners, foster student engagement, and promote an inclusive classroom environment.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Gender, Secondary School, Students, Teachers' Self-Efficacy

Introduction

The extent to which the goals of public secondary education are achieved is often reflected in the academic achievement of students. Achievement at the primary school level plays a foundational role in enabling progression to higher levels of education and serves as a critical benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of

educational systems and policies, as noted by Carrillo-Lopez et al. (2022). It enables learners to advance into secondary and tertiary education. At the secondary level, students' academic achievement is widely regarded as an indicator of school effectiveness and a vital factor influencing both individual development and national advancement. Onyekwelu (2024) affirmed that academic success at this level reflects not only the efficiency of schools but also the general well-being of society. Adepoju and Akinwumi (2019) asserted that academic achievement should be understood as a multidimensional concept rather than a single outcome. In a similar vein, Ifelunni et al. (2019) defined academic achievement as the outcome of students' learning efforts within the school context, typically measured through assessments and examinations administered by teachers. The achievement of educational objectives is strongly influenced by the extent to which teachers perform their assigned duties. Academic achievement is often identified through test results and examination marks awarded by subject teachers. It can also be described as a term that reflects a student's level of academic attainment. The matter of academic achievement remains a key concern for educators, learners, parents, guardians, and other stakeholders within the educational sector (Ahmed et al., 2022).

Teachers' capacity to manage their responsibilities and schedules effectively is fundamental to educational success. In recent years, however, there has been growing concern regarding declining student performance in certain subjects across secondary schools in Anambra State. This issue has been linked to several challenges, including insufficient teaching materials, and behavioural issues (Parcutilo & Baluyos, 2019). Nevertheless, one potentially significant yet frequently overlooked factor is teachers' self-efficacy.

Teacher efficacy refers to the confidence teachers have in their ability to positively influence student learning outcomes. It reflects the belief that educators can shape, or at the very least significantly impact, students' academic success and motivation (Ntsayakgosi et al., 2024). Studies have shown that teachers' self-efficacy is closely associated with students' academic adjustment, teachers' classroom behaviours and instructional practices, as well as their own professional well-being, including job satisfaction, a sense of accomplishment, and dedication to the profession (Zee & Koomen, 2022). Ninkovic and Floric (2018) describe teacher self-efficacy as a teacher's perception of their own ability to effectively plan and execute actions required to achieve specific educational goals within a particular context. It encompasses several domains, notably classroom management, the use of instructional strategies, and student engagement (Sokmen, 2021). Self-efficacy in classroom management refers to the teacher's belief in their capacity to handle disruptive behaviours and create an environment conducive to learning. Instructional self-efficacy, in contrast, involves confidence in delivering effective teaching methods and strategies that support students' understanding and participation. Finally, self-efficacy related to student engagement concerns the teacher's ability to inspire and maintain students' active involvement in the learning process (Lazarides et al., 2020).

Teachers' self-efficacy has been identified as a significant factor affecting students' academic achievement. Educators with high self-efficacy are more likely to implement effective teaching strategies, manage classrooms

efficiently, and engage students actively, all of which contribute to improved academic outcomes. Swarnalatha (2019) found that teacher self-efficacy positively impacts secondary school students' academic achievement. Similarly, Altaf et al. (2023) reported that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are interconnected with student academic success, emphasizing the need for strategies that enhance self-efficacy to improve teaching practices and student learning outcomes. Also, Abubakar (2020) reported a significant positive correlation between teacher self-efficacy and students' performance in Islamic Studies in senior secondary schools. These findings highlight the critical role of teacher self-efficacy in shaping students' academic achievements across different educational settings. Furthermore, gender has been considered as a moderating factor on the relationship between teachers self-efficacy and students academic achievement.

Academic Achievement Gender has been explored as a moderating factor in the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement. Studies indicate that gender differences can influence teaching practices and attitudes, which in turn affect student achievement. Hastedt et al. (2021) revealed that female teachers exhibited more positive teaching practices and attitudes compared to their male counterparts, leading to higher student achievement in mathematics and science. This suggests that the gender of teachers can have a substantial impact on their self-efficacy beliefs and, consequently, on student outcomes. Furthermore, Apau (2021) reported that male teachers often demonstrate higher levels of self-efficacy in classroom management and student engagement compared to female teachers, potentially due to cultural perceptions of gender roles. On the other hand, Ahmed et al. (2022) revealed that while teachers' self-efficacy positively influenced students' self-efficacy in biology, female students exhibited higher self-efficacy levels than their male counterparts. In contrast, Baji (2020) reported that male students had higher academic self-efficacy and achievement levels compared to female students. This phenomenon is attributed to increased comfort and encouragement in classroom interactions (Usman et al., 2022). Conversely, male students may benefit from male teachers who exhibit strong classroom management and student engagement skills (Omonije et al., 2016). These studies despite their results were not conducted in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. It is against this background that the researcher investigated the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic performance in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

The issue of poor academic achievement among students in secondary schools within the Awka Education Zone of Anambra State has become increasingly evident. Despite various efforts to improve the quality of education, many students continue to perform below standard, particularly in core subjects critical to their academic progression. This trend threatens the realisation of educational goals and limits students' opportunities for advancement to higher levels of learning. Field observations carried out by the researcher in selected schools within the zone suggest that students struggle considerably in subjects such as Mathematics. This consistent underperformance not only affects individual students but also raises broader concerns about the overall

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effectiveness of teaching and learning processes in these schools. While several factors may contribute to this problem, such as limited instructional resources and socio-economic challenges, the situation appears to be significantly influenced by the self-efficacy of teachers. Teachers who lack confidence in their ability to deliver subject content, manage classroom dynamics, or engage students meaningfully may inadvertently contribute to poor academic outcomes. Therefore, the observed low achievement among students in secondary schools across the Awka Education Zone may be linked to variations in teachers' self-efficacy levels. This study seeks to investigate this possible relationship and provide insights into how strengthening teacher self-efficacy could enhance student academic performance.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone, Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.
2. Examine the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Methodology

This study employed a correlational research design to examine the relationship between variables. The research was conducted in Anambra State, located in the South-Eastern region of Nigeria. The state was selected due to its historical recognition as one of the most educationally advanced in the country, particularly for its consistent high performance in national examinations such as WAEC. However, recent records indicate a downward trend

in students' academic outcomes, with the state no longer maintaining its former top position. This decline has prompted growing concerns about the underlying causes.

The population of study comprised 5,550 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students across 267 government-owned secondary schools in Anambra State. Among this group, 2,444 were male students and 3,106 were female students. From this population, a sample of 400 students consisting of 200 males and 200 females were selected for the study. A multistage sampling procedure was adopted to derive the sample. Initially, two local government areas; Awka South and Anaocha were randomly chosen. Thereafter, two public secondary schools were selected from each zone using stratified random sampling, bringing the total number of participating schools to four. At the final stage, a cluster sampling method was applied, selecting one arm of SS2 students from each of the ten schools. Since each selected arm comprised 40 students, a total of 160 students participated in the study.

Data were collected using a researcher-designed questionnaire titled Teachers' Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (TSEQ) and through Students' Academic Achievement Scores (SAAS). The TSEQ comprised 20 items on teachers' self-efficacy. The instrument is structured on a four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). For students' academic performance, English Language scores were obtained from the Recording Department of the Post Primary Schools Service Commission (PPSSC), Awka, in 2024. Mathematics was chosen as it is a compulsory subject and reflects general academic proficiency. To ensure the instruments' validity, copies of the questionnaire, along with the study's objectives, research questions, and hypotheses, were submitted to three academic experts in the Department of Educational Foundations at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam. These experts reviewed the instruments for face and construct validity, assessing clarity, relevance, and comprehensiveness. Based on their feedback, improvements were made, including refining ambiguous items, correcting instructions, assigning proper titles to clusters, and removing double-barrelled questions. Reliability testing was conducted through a pilot study involving 20 SS2 students from Onitsha Education Zone, who were excluded from the main study. The data obtained were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding reliability coefficient of 0.87, suggesting that the instrument was dependable. Out of 160 copies of the questionnaire administered, 148 copies were returned in good condition and used for data analysis.

Data analysis involved the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistics to address the research questions, evaluating the extent to which teachers' communication patterns could predict students' academic achievement. Hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using SPSS version 26. A positive r coefficient indicated a direct relationship between variables, whereas a negative coefficient implied an inverse relationship. In interpreting results, a p -value less than or equal to 0.05 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, signifying a statistically significant relationship. Conversely, p -values above 0.05 indicated no significant correlation, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone?

Table 1: Pearson Correlation between Teachers’ Self-Efficacy and Students’ Academic Achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	148	0.72	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson’s correlation (r) presented in Table 1 shows that the correlation between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone was 0.72. This value indicates a high positive relationship. This implies that as teachers self-efficacy increases, students academic achievement in public secondary schools also increases and at a high rate. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone?

Table 2: Pearson Correlation between Teachers’ Self-Efficacy and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone

Variables	N	r	Remarks
Male:			
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	57	0.69	High positive relationship
Female:			
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	91	0.71	High positive relationship

The result of the Pearson’s correlation (r) presented in Table 2 reveals that there was a high positive relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and academic achievement among both male and female students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. This is demonstrated in the r values which are 0.69 and 0.71 for the males and females respectively.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Teachers’ Self-Efficacy and Students’ Academic Achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remark
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	148	0.72	0.00	Significant

The results in Table 3 show that there was a significant positive relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone, $r = 0.72$, $p < 0.05$. Since the p-value was less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there was a significant relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Teachers’ Self-Efficacy and Academic Achievement of Male and Female Secondary School Students in Awka Education Zone

Variables	N	r	p-value	Remarks
Male:				
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	57	0.69	0.000	Significant
Female:				
Teachers’ Self-Efficacy Students Academic Achievement	91	0.71	0.000	Significant

The results on Table 4 showed a significant positive relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone. Since the p-value for both male and female students was less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis stating that there would be no significant relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and academic achievement of male and female secondary school students in Awka Education Zone was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed a high positive relationship between teachers’ self-efficacy and students’ academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. Two factors could account for this finding. First, teachers with high self-efficacy are more confident in their ability to deliver instructional content effectively, which enhances students’ understanding and retention of subject matter. Second, such teachers are more likely to

adopt innovative teaching strategies, manage classrooms efficiently, and motivate students to perform better academically. This finding is in agreement with that of Swarnalatha (2019) who noted that teacher self-efficacy positively impacts secondary school students' academic achievement. Similarly, Altaf et al. (2023) found that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are strongly linked to student academic success, highlighting the importance of fostering high self-efficacy among teachers to improve instructional quality and student learning outcomes. Additionally, Abubakar (2020) documented that teacher self-efficacy significantly correlates with students' performance in Islamic Studies at the senior secondary school level.

Furthermore, the findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This result corroborates with Altaf et al. (2023) who emphasized that teachers' belief in their professional competence enhances their effectiveness in the classroom, leading to improved student outcomes. In the same vein, Swarnalatha (2019) stated that highly efficacious teachers demonstrate greater commitment and creativity in teaching, which directly contributes to students' academic improvement.

The findings of this study revealed a high positive relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the academic achievement of male and female students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This finding indicates that teachers' self-efficacy could influence students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone irrespective of gender. This finding is consistent with the findings of Ahmed et al. (2022) who reported that teachers' self-efficacy positively influenced students' self-efficacy in biology, and that female students demonstrated higher self-efficacy levels than their male counterparts. They documented that teachers with high self-efficacy create more engaging and supportive learning environments, which in turn foster academic growth in both male and female students, supporting the present study's assertion that teacher confidence is a key determinant of student achievement. Furthermore, Baji (2020) found that male students had higher academic self-efficacy and achievement than female students, suggesting that gender dynamics may influence how students respond to instructional strategies. These findings suggest that while teachers' self-efficacy benefits students of both genders, male and female students may experience its effects differently depending on subject matter, learning environment, and teacher-student interactions. Additionally, the findings of this study revealed a significant relationship between teachers' gender and students' academic performance. This aligns with the findings of Usman et al. (2022) who reported that female students performed better academically when taught by female teachers, particularly in English and mathematics, attributing this to increased comfort and encouragement in the classroom. Similarly, Omonije et al. (2016) found that male students benefitted more from male teachers who demonstrated strong classroom management and engagement strategies.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed a high positive relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and the academic performance of male and female students in public secondary schools in Awka Education Zone. This finding

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indicates that teachers' self-efficacy significantly influences students' academic achievement irrespective of gender. The findings further revealed that both male and female students benefit from teachers who demonstrate a strong sense of self-efficacy, though the specific effects may vary by gender. These findings support existing research which shows that students taught by confident and competent teachers tend to perform better academically.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Post Primary Schools Services Commission (PPSSC) and school administrators in public secondary schools should prioritise the professional development of teachers to strengthen their instructional self-efficacy. This can be achieved through regular training workshops, peer coaching, and opportunities for reflective teaching practices.
2. The State Ministry of Education and curriculum planners should ensure that teacher preparation programmes integrate components that build confidence in classroom management, instructional delivery, and assessment practices.
3. School principals and educational supervisors should implement mentorship systems where experienced teachers with high self-efficacy mentor less experienced colleagues. This will help create a culture of collaboration and continuous improvement in teaching practices.
4. Teachers should be encouraged to adopt teaching approaches that accommodate diverse learners, foster student engagement, and promote an inclusive classroom environment. These strategies will ensure that both male and female students receive equitable support in achieving academic success.

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